

Analytical Solution of the Schrödinger Equation with an Exponential Type Mass Depending on the Spatial Variable

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Abstract:

In the present work, we proceed to study the Schrödinger equation with dependent mass position. From the resulting partial differential equations, we obtain exact analytical solutions governed by Bessel functions. The exact solution of Schrödinger's equation for a particle with dependent position of the mass (PDM) is a "half-harmonic potential" defined in a Hilbert space. The harmonic oscillator is carried by the wave function $\psi(x)$ through the Bessel function. The magnitude of $\psi(x)$ increases dramatically as the values of the spatial coordinate become larger and larger. This growth is all the more marked as the mass parameter increases. It appears that the wave

function has the same asymptotic behavior as the solution of Airy's equation of the second kind. Their oscillations have the same amplitudes near infinity. The mass parameter has a great importance and influence on the mass and also on the wave potential. It is a control parameter in the Schrödinger equations (PDM).

Keywords: *Schrodinger equation, Position-dependent mass, half-Harmonic potential, exact solution.*

Introduction

The study of the position-dependent mass Schrodinger equation (PDM) has long been of interest to many scientists. Among quantum mechanical physicists for example PDM has had a considerable impact on the understanding of particle behavior. In recent years, position-dependent mass mechanics systems have received considerable attention from physicists in general. Interest stems from the relevance of the PDM context to describe crystal behavior and semiconductor nanodevices. These applications stimulated the study of the different theoretical aspects of the PDM Schrödinger equation: research of exact analytical solution, form invariance, point canonical transformation and the relation to theories in curved spaces (Bagchi et al., 2005). Such an understanding of PDM allows to define functions of quantum waves in a sometimes complex field. Several methods for

solving the PDM Schrödinger equation have already been designed with the use of potentials and mass functions (Jamshir, Lari & Hassanabadi, 2021).

However, there are few studies regarding the behavior and understanding of wave functions in PDM systems. Nevertheless, the mathematical properties of PDM and its applications have been intensively studied. One of the main objectives of these studies is to obtain exact solutions of the Schrodinger equations with a variable mass term. From the mathematical point of view, the second order linear Schrödinger equation can be reformulated as a first order Riccati equation (Polyanin & Zaitsev, 2018) through the Cole-Hopf Transformation. This representation not only provides a deeper insight into the mathematical properties of quantum systems, but also leads to exact analytical solutions of the Schrodinger

equation that can be used to describe the behavior of certain quantum systems. In the solution of these Schrodinger equations with position dependent effective mass some authors have obtained results by the mathematical theory of potentials (Ovando et al., 2009). Others have solved the equations from the MDPs with specific choices of position-dependent mass function and Morse oscillator potential by means of the Nikiforov - Uvarov method combined with the Pekeris approximation scheme (Abdalla, Eleuch & Barakat, 2013). Others have used Shannon and Fisher entropy models to link PDM and alternative entropies with the aim of obtaining a Hermitian-like quantum Hamiltonian (Falaye, Serrano & Dong, 2016).

In this research paper we use as a working hypothesis a pointwise canonical transformation method of PDM (Jafarpour & Ashtari, 2011). This with a semi-harmonic potential, we solve the Schrödinger equation for a particle whose mass depends on the position $m(x) = \frac{x^\lambda}{\tau^2}$, where τ is a real parameter that provides the required dimension for $m(x)$.

The PDM that we consider in this study can also be reformulated in an exponential form already used in other research articles (Mustafa, 2021). A simple calculation shows that $m(x)$ is increasing when the parameter λ increases.

It should be noted that the mass that we consider in this study has been slightly modified from used in previous studies (Mustafa, 2021). Such a choice allows simplifying the physical models with fewer parameters. We can thus obtain analytically and with more mathematical clarity energy potentials or waves functions described by series Bessel functions.

The Schrödinger equation with position-dependent mass and exact solution

In standard non-relativistic quantum mechanics, the kinetic energy operator usually takes the simple form $\hat{T} = \frac{p}{2m}$ where m is the mass (constant) of the particle and p is the momentum

operator. However, this kinetic operator is not very well defined for a particle with a position dependent mass $m = m(x)$. Thus, for the PDM case, it is appropriate to order the mass with respect to the momentum operators in order to generalize the standard kinetic energy operator \hat{T} so that the PDM can be constructed.

In this paper, we use the generalized Hermitian kinetic operator (Bagchi et al., 2005):

$$T = \frac{1}{4} [m(x)^a p m(x)^b p m(x)^c + m(x)^c p m(x)^b p m(x)^a] \quad (1)$$

where a, b and c are ambiguous parameters satisfying the equation $a + b + c = -1$.

The first term of the above equation is added here in order to include in the general expression the usual symmetry.

Then one can see that the above operator will be (von Roos & Mavromatis, 1985):

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \left[p \frac{1}{m(x)} p \right], \quad (2)$$

For an arbitrary external potential $V(x)$, the non-ambiguous PDM Schrödinger equation takes the form:

$$-\frac{\hbar}{2} \left(\frac{1}{m(x)} \psi'(x) \right)' + (V(x) - E) \psi(x) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where \hbar is the Planck constant and $\psi(x)$ is the wave function introduced in the Schrödinger equation for the mass distribution mentioned above

Taking into account the mass expression defined in the introduction, equation (3) becomes:

$$\psi''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{2} \psi'(x) + \frac{2x^\lambda}{\tau^2 \hbar^2} [E - V(x)] \psi(x) = 0, \quad (4)$$

In order to analytically solve the non-linear equation (4), we use a decoupled method (Diouf & Zidi, 2005).

It consists in breaking down the wave function $\psi(x)$ into the form:

$$\psi(x) = f(x) + g(x)\cos(wx) \quad (5)$$

We get the equation in f and g :

$$\begin{aligned} & f''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{x}f'(x) + \frac{2x^\lambda}{\tau^2 h^2} [E - V(x)]f(x) + \\ & \left[g''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{x}g'(x) - w^2g(x) + \frac{2x^\lambda}{\tau^2 h^2} [E - V(x)]g(x) \right] \cos(wx) + \\ & \left[-2wg'(x) + \frac{\lambda w}{x}g(x) \right] \sin(wx) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & F(f''(x), f'(x), f(x)) + \\ & G(g''(x), g'(x), g(x)) \cos(wx) + \\ & H(g'(x), g(x)) \sin(wx) = 0, \forall x \end{aligned}$$

and whatever the choice of w .

This implies that:

$$\begin{cases} F(f''(x), f'(x), f(x)) = 0 \\ G(g''(x), g'(x), g(x)) = 0, \\ H(g'(x), g(x)) = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} f''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{x}f'(x) + \frac{2x^\lambda}{\tau^2 h^2} [E - V(x)]f(x) = 0 \\ g''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{x}g'(x) - w^2g(x) + \frac{2x^\lambda}{\tau^2 h^2} [E - V(x)]g(x) = 0, \\ -2wg'(x) + \frac{\lambda w}{x}g(x) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Solving the first-order differential equation (7₃) is immediate:

$$g(x) = C_0 x^{\lambda/2}, \quad (8)$$

with C_0 an integration constant.

These three independent solutions belong to a solution space. The functions F, G, H form a base of the solution space.

In mathematics, the problem of reducing a system of differential equations to its simplest, normal form was posed by Poincaré (1928) and developed by Liapunov. In the resolution of these equations, although based on the work of these two authors, we study the problems of nonlinear oscillations.

We then obtain the following system of differential equations:

By reporting the solution (8) in the equation (7₂) we obtain the expression of the potential:

$$V(x) = E - \frac{\tau^2 h^2}{2x^\lambda} \left[w^2 + \frac{\lambda(\lambda+2)}{4x^2} \right], \quad (9)$$

By transferring the expression of the potential $V(x)$ defined above into equation (7₁), we arrive at the nonlinear differential equation of the second order:

$$f''(x) - \frac{\lambda}{x}f'(x) + \left[w^2 + \frac{\lambda(\lambda+2)}{4x^2}\right]f(x) = 0, \quad (10)$$

This equation (10) is a Bessel equation and therefore the function $f(x)$ is a Bessel function.

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= x^{\frac{1+\lambda}{2}} Z_\nu(wx) \\ &= x^{\frac{1+\lambda}{2}} [A_0 J_\nu(wx) + B_0 J_{-\nu}(wx)] \end{aligned}, \quad (11)$$

with $\nu = 1/2$, A_0 and B_0 integration constants.

The exact analytical expression of the general solution of the PDM Schrödinger equation whose form is defined in (5), taking into account the results of (8) and (11) is given by:

$$\psi(x) = x^{\frac{1+\lambda}{2}} [A_0 J_\nu(wx) + B_0 J_{-\nu}(wx)] + C_0 x^{\lambda/2} \cos(wx), \quad (12)$$

If $\nu \in \frac{1}{2} + \mathbb{Z}$, the Bessel function are elementary functions:

$$\begin{aligned} J_{1/2}(t) &= Y_{-1/2}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi t}} \sin(t) \\ J_{-1/2}(t) &= -Y_{1/2}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi t}} \cos(t) \end{aligned},$$

The wave function can then be written in the more condensed or simplified form:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x) &= x^{\lambda/2} \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi w}} [A_0 \sin(wx) + B_0 \cos(wx)] + C_0 \cos(wx) \right] \\ &= x^{\lambda/2} \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi w}} [A_0 \sin(wx) + B_0 \cos(wx)] + C_0 \cos(wx) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Analytical approximations should relate power and asymptotic behavior in the numerical series,

The Bessel functions have certain analogies with the trigonometric functions for their oscillating character but with amplitude and frequency modulation (they are damped).

The analytical solution of (10) is given by:

especially in the case of a mechanical or electrodynamic study.

The change of sign every time “ $w x$ ” makes a turn introduces a series of discontinuities into asymptotic developments called Stokes phenomenon.

Results and Discussion

We simulate in the graph below the variation of the potential $\psi(x)$ according to the spatial variable x .

Figure 1. Function Introduced in the Schrodinger Equation for the Mass Distribution vs x for Values of the Mass Parameter a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 .

Function introduced in the Schrodinger equation for the mass distribution vs x for values of the mass parameter $\lambda = a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4$.

Figure 2. Function Introduced in the Schrodinger Equation for the Mass Distribution vs x for a Value of the Mass Parameter a3

Function introduced in the Schrodinger equation for the mass distribution vs x for a value of the mass parameter $\lambda = a3$.

Figure 3. Evolution of the Mass vs x, for a1,a2,a3,a4

It can be seen from this graph that the amplitude of $\psi(x)$ increases considerably when the values of the spatial coordinate becomes larger and larger. This growth is even more marked when the mass parameter increases.

We have obtained analytical results for the potential that governs Schrodinger's equation for a distribution of mass and energy potential. It appears from these resolutions that these

functions are harmonic and increase in algebraic value according to the growth of λ . We can note that the analytical solutions obtained derive from the conditions of integrability of the mass function, the energy potential E and the wave function $\psi(x)$. They are in a Hilbert space whose norm is the scalar product. These different potentials can generate a wide variety of position-dependent mass functions. Solutions from Schrödinger's equation with a PDM are presented as series of Bessel-type functions. The harmonic oscillator is carried by the $\psi(x)$ wave function through the Bessel function $J_\nu(u)$. By increasing values of $x = [\tau^2 m]^{1/\lambda}$, it appears that the wave function has the same asymptotic behavior as the solution of Airy's equation of the second kind. Their oscillations have the same amplitudes around $+\infty$.

Conclusion

We have obtained exact analytical solutions for a PDM system governed by a harmonic potential. We have observed that each energy level is an increasing function of λ the wave function obtained from a harmonic oscillator given by a Bessel function.

The evolution of the mass $m(x)$ as a function of the spatial variable x is polynomial type growth. This growth is all the more marked as the mass parameter λ increases. We deduce that the mass parameter has a great importance in addition to the mass and also to the wave function. It could act as a control parameter in Schrodinger equations (PDM).

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